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CLASSIC ENGLISH DRAMA: GENDER PECULIARITIES OF CHARACTERS' SPEECH

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Abstract

The article under consideration is devoted to the peculiarities of language and speech behavior of the characters of the classic English drama. Approaching the problem of differences in the speech of men and women from the standpoint of the theory of linguistic personality and taking into account the social conditionality of these differences, the concept of gender is proposed to be understood as dynamic, culturally determined social characteristics of men and women - carriers of different world views, which are reconstructed in their main features based on linguistic means of both oral and written speech. Relying on the theoretical foundations of gender linguistics, the article's authors identify the fundamental features of the language and behavior of the main characters of classic English drama. The article identifies and systematizes the gender peculiarities of communicative behavior that playwrights give to male and female characters when depicting situations of informal intergender communication in English dramatic works, as well as lexical and stylistic gender differences in the verbal behavior of characters. General scientific methods (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, generalization) and linguistic methods are used in the study.

Keywords: gender, communicative behavior, communicative stereotypes, character language, English drama.

Introduction.

Modern linguistics is increasingly interested in studying the functional side of language since the language system can be adequately understood only during its direct implementation. The appeal to the human factor [Bessonova, 2002] demonstrates the place and role of language in human life and its development as a personality. The communicative direction in linguistics considers communication as a human activity to exchange various information to achieve specific communicative and non-communicative goals. Communication is carried out through language and ensures the interaction of people in society. Communicative linguistics studies the properties of language and speech units manifested in communication when partners exchange information, thoughts, feelings, and points of view to solve linguistic and extralinguistic tasks [Borysenko 1997, 11].

The study of communication is closely related to the analysis of human communicative behavior, which is actively studied in various fields of linguistics: psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, linguistic stylistics, cognitive linguistics, and pragmalinguistics. The study of the gender aspect of communicative behavior is intended to complement and expand the study of the communication of works of art.

The need for a linguistic interpretation of interpersonal relations, in turn, has made it possible to develop new areas of research, one of which is gender linguistics. It focuses on the dependence of language function-

ing on gender differences that manifest in verbal communication and are determined by the sex of the communicators. Gender differentiation is one of the universal phenomena studied by the humanities, and the communicator's gender is one of the socio-psychological factors whose influence on human communicative behavior is of interest to modern linguists. The term gender, borrowed from the social sciences, in modern linguistics refers to a set of social, cultural, and psychological phenomena correlated with the sex of an individual.

Approaching the problem of differences in the speech of men and women from the standpoint of the theory of linguistic personality (the concept of "linguistic personality" can refer to both an individual and a group of people who share a common worldview) and taking into account the social determination of these differences, the term gender is proposed to be understood as dynamic, culturally determined social characteristics of men and women - carriers of different worldviews, which are reconstructed in their main features based on linguistic means of both oral and written speech. The study of gender differences in communicative behavior is possible both in authentic communication and based on artistic communicative interaction [Semashko, 2010]. Mary Talbot states, "Men and women are different because language positions us differently" (Talbot, 2010, p. 110).

The analysis of the speech of a dramatic work not as a ready-made sample of honest communication but

as a reflection of real communication, taking into account its unique functional character, is contained in the works of various researchers. The realistic drama authors model characters' speech based on the desire to convey the "truth of life," guided by their knowledge of how everyday communication takes place in a particular situation. In other words, when creating a speech characterization of characters, the playwright is guided by stereotypes of gendered behavior.

The relevance of the topic of our study, which is carried out in the context of communicative linguistics, is determined by the general direction of communicative linguistics towards establishing gender peculiarities of language and speech behavior of characters in modern English drama. The study of gender differences in character speech is relevant because it allows us to trace how the linguistic characteristics of the characters reflect the communicative stereotypes of the playwright, a native speaker of British English. The language of dramatic works, combining the features of the language of fiction and colloquial speech, is a communication created by the playwright based on real communication.

Methodology.

The purpose of our study is to identify and systematize the gender peculiarities of communicative behavior that playwrights give to male and female characters when depicting situations of informal intergender communication in classical English dramatic works, as well as lexical and stylistic gender differences in the verbal behavior of characters. The study uses general scientific and linguistic methods (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, generalization). The continuous sampling method was used to identify the units of analysis. The descriptive method allowed for the taxonomy and interpretation of the concept of "gender" in linguistics. The contextual method contributed to the identification of linguistic and extra-linguistic gender features of linguistic units of modern English drama.

According to T. Semashko, the term "gender" came to the modern linguistic paradigm from the social sciences much later than in other humanities, when gender studies became an interdisciplinary field. Initially, work in this area emerged in the West, and the first systematic descriptions of male and female features of language and speech were made based on the languages of the Germanic and Romance language groups. Today, this process is so rapid that we can confidently talk about the emergence of another branch of national linguistics - linguistic gender studies or gender linguistics.

Although the term "gender" is recognized by most researchers, there are some difficulties due to the relative novelty of this concept and its peculiarities. The term "gender" originated in the English-speaking world and is an English homonym for the grammatical gender category. Some researchers analyzing the gender differentiation of society and related processes use the old terms but include in their considerations the social and cultural significance of gender. In many works, the concepts of "sex" and "gender" are used in parallel; inaccuracies arise depending on the language in which the study is written, as well as when translating foreign-language works into Ukrainian; the author's conceptual

position is essential when choosing terminology" [Semashko, 2010, 167].

Vilkova O. (2005) argues that the nature of the functions of gender stereotypes of our time, as constructive or destructive, should be analyzed not only by the impact of gender stereotypes on the social life of today but also by the nature of stereotypes that have functioned throughout the existence of human society, since stereotypical representations are stable and multifunctional formations that do not disappear and do not arise simultaneously.

When analyzing fictional dialogue, it should be noted that dialogue is the leading way of portraying a character in literature. The peculiarity of dialogue in a literary text is that it is usually structurally and stylistically opposed to the author's narrative. While the author's narrative is mainly written speech, reflected in syntax and style, the characters' speech always imitates live oral verbal communication (Martyniuk, 2004, p. 43).

Lakoff points out several features of the female language in her book. She believes that females prefer concrete words that closely relate to life. Females use expletives softer, but males often speak in a firm tone. The author argues that gender differences in discourse production are highly culture-specific; thus, the same patterns of language interactions should not be expected across different cultures.

Main Part.

Interest in studying speech activity has drawn attention to problems related to the human factor in language. One of them is the most appropriate choice of linguistic means and ways of their integration, determined by the participants' gender in the character speech of dramatic works. An individual's verbal behavior is a particular case of his/her communicative behavior. By verbal behavior, we mean the actualization and interaction of linguistic units in a statement to build a pragmatically correct statement.

The analysis of dramatic works shows that the differences in the verbal behavior of characters (men and women) in informal intergender communication are primarily observed in adjectives that implement a general assessment. Evaluative words are directly related to the speaker and reflect his/her attitude to the surrounding reality. The general evaluation is an axiological result of the cognitive process, expressing the attitude to the world.

Quantitative analysis shows the percentage of certain lexical items used in the statements of characters of a particular gender to the total number of these in the statements of characters of both genders in informal intergender communication, which is 100%. The expression of a generally positive assessment in the situation of informal intergender communication is more typical for the verbal behavior of female characters (65% of word uses) and less typical for the statements of male characters (35% of word uses), which indicates the importance of positive assessment in the verbal behavior of female characters compared to male characters.

In addition, differences are observed in the qualitative composition of this vocabulary. In the analyzed material, we have identified gender differences in using

such positive adjectives as sweet, admirable, lovely, charming, marvelous, gorgeous, fantastic, terrific, nice, fine, splendid, and their derived adverbs. At the same time, in the situation of informal intergender communication, the verbal behavior of female characters, regardless of age, is more typical for the use of the following adjectives of general positive evaluation and their derivatives: admirable (female characters account for 100% of all word uses), charming (80%), sweet (78%), lovely (75%), gorgeous (75%), marvelous (67%), nice (65%) to characterize objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality. For example, when communicating with friends:

MARIAN. I thought you did admirably in the circumstances (Dryden, 1982: 8);

JOAN. Oh yes, the Commander, I met him last night. A charming man, I thought (Manktelow, 1979, p.3);

FLEUR. Lovely bird. It's a lovely, lovely bird (Ayckbourn, 1983, p. 56);

MONICA. And he's so nice: gorgeous in his pin-stripes last week, this week? (Murphy, 1990, p.14);

DIANA. It was all right, you know. Everything was marvelous (Browne, 1976, p. 50).

These lexical units are less typical for the verbal behavior of male characters in informal intergender communication. However, they are found in their statements, indicating significant gender differences in the linguistic competence that playwrights endow their characters with. At the same time, these units are used to characterize the verbal behavior of male characters by playwrights of both sexes. This is due to the absence of a severe influence of the author's gender on the creation of verbal behavior of characters of the opposite sex. For example, in a conversation between a married couple:

KEITH. A lovely day (Ayckbourn, 1983, p. 16).

Or in a conversation between lovers:

CLIFFORD. You are sweet, Ellen (Rayburn, 1977 p. 43).

Of the above lexical units, the adjectives nice and marvelous are the most typical for the verbal behavior of male characters, while the adjective charming is the least typical, and the unit admirable does not occur in the utterances of male characters. This shows that evaluative vocabulary is more stable with female verbal behavior in the linguistic picture of the world that male characters possess. The units nice and marvelous are the most neutral for the verbal behavior of male characters.

Even when expressing a generally positive assessment in informal intergender communicative interaction, characters of different genders use characteristic vocabulary in the same pair of lines, which also reflects the differences in their linguistic worldview and is revealed when they talk

- about weather:

CLIFFORD. It's a splendid morning.

ELLIE. Lovely (Rayburn, 1977, p. 48);

- about music:

LINDSEY. Mm. Lovely.

DICKON. It's genius (Hastings, 1979, p. 25).

In intergender communication, a positive male assessment may be more reserved than a female one:

LINDSEY. It is charming.

DICKON. Perhaps it's okay musically (Hastings, 1979, p. 3).

1979, p. 24).

The qualitative differences in the expression of the overall negative assessment are related to creating the image of female characters' restraint during its implementation. For example, when a female character addresses a male acquaintance:

MRS. MOORE. Not very nice, is it, just waiting (Manktelow, 1977, p. 35).

In addition, to express a generally negative assessment of the statements of male characters, the vocabulary of a lowered stylistic tone is used: bloody, rotten, and sodding, which is not typical for the verbal behavior of female characters. For example, in a conversation between a married couple, a male character states the fact that his shop is not as famous as a supermarket:

RAY. Six women pass the shop; they don't stop, they're off down the supermarket for their frozen bloody mini-joints, Chinese-rotten takeaways, pork-blinkin' batch shop, cod, and soddin' chips... (Davis, 1982, p. 3).

The analysis allows us to assume that male and female characters choose mainly different lexical items to express their general positive evaluation. Female characters are characterized by a tendency to openly and exaggeratedly express positive evaluations and use a broader range of evaluative adjectives. In contrast, male characters' remarks are characterized by restraint in their manifestation. This fact reflects significant differences in the linguistic worldview and communicative competence of men and women. Using positive evaluation demonstrates the character's generally positive attitude, contributes to creating a constructive, friendly atmosphere during communication, indicates a friendly attitude towards the interlocutor, and is considered one of the components of the positive politeness strategy.

The implementation of a generally negative assessment of the verbal behavior of male characters in a situation of intergender communication indicates the disregard for the official norms of British society, according to which the use of the stylistic vocabulary of a lowered tone is considered indecent.

Thus, the use of adjectives of general negative evaluation and stylistically reduced vocabulary for its realization is more typical for the statements of male characters. Using negative evaluation in the characters' statements conveys the speaker's general negative mood. It can signal a critical perception of the surrounding reality and the interlocutor, particularly his/her communicative behavior. Thus, negative evaluation hinders the creation of a constructive environment during communicative interaction. The gender specifics of implementing general evaluation means are due to the differences in the linguistic picture of the world and the levels of communicative competence of characters of different sexes created by playwrights. The

gender-specific features of implementing general evaluation reflect the stereotypes of gender communicative behavior in modern society.

Words acquire a stylistic coloring based on the constant association associated with using a lexical item in certain areas and communication situations. Let us analyze the gender aspect of stylistically colored lexical items such as words of foreign origin, barbarisms, and professional vocabulary.

Use of words of foreign origin and barbarisms

Barbarianisms are words and phrases borrowed from other languages but, to a certain extent, "adapted" to the norms of the recipient language and usually used. However, their foreign origin is quite clear. Words and phrases of foreign origin are lexical units of another language used mainly in literary speech. According to domestic researchers, drawing a clear line between words of foreign language origin and barbarisms is difficult. Since their stylistic functions are identical, we will consider these groups together.

Our analysis of dramatic works shows that words of foreign origin and barbarisms are widely used in the statements of characters who are native speakers of British English in their communication with their compatriots. A gender analysis of the characters' speech proves that the use of this group of vocabulary is typical for the verbal behavior of characters of both sexes in intergender communicative interaction but is more typical for the statements of male characters. This vocabulary is found twice as often in the utterances of male characters as in those of the opposite sex. The use of words of foreign origin and barbarism has different pragmatic purposes. For example, a significant part of this vocabulary is made up of names of drinks and dishes used in the statements of characters of both sexes:

KEVIN. I made a really terrific quiche Loraine, and she dug a tree out of the garden (Harris, 1980, p. 46);

CRESSIDA. This is sparkling Saumer, méthode champenoise (Edgar, 1987, p. 73);

DENNIS. The old vino del plonk (Harris, 1980, p. 21).

In addition, the use of barbarism helps a male character to make an impression of an erudite interlocutor and, ultimately, to raise his status in a woman's eyes. For example, a student waiter uses barbarism to convey the atmosphere of a cafe:

WENDY. I'm drinking in the atmosphere - as the brochure says. Warm night, water, flowers, colored lights - it's fun.

WAITER. Very kitch.

WENDY. Kitch?

Waiter. A German word is difficult to translate. It means ornate, obvious, overdone, a little vulgar. Therefore fashionable (Vooght, 1980, p. 8).

In the statements of male characters, barbarisms and words of foreign origin are used to mislead the less-educated female interlocutor. For example, an educated waiter misleads a capricious but uneducated customer by using a fictitious French name for a dish and the phrase "deep freeze" as the name of the person who invented it:

WAITER. I'd like to suggest something very special. Boeuf durfrappe au pommes de terre brules a beef dish for the discerning.

LILIAN. Special, you say?

Waiter. Very. And delicious. It was created by Monsieur Gelee Profond for the Russian Royal Family, who all tended to have delicate stomachs (Vooght, 1980, p. 7).

Thus, the use of barbarisms and words of foreign origin is a characteristic feature of the verbal behavior of male characters, indicates a more important place of these lexical items in verbal behavior, and aims to increase the status of the speaker, reflecting the communicative stereotype of a man's desire to strengthen his position in intergender communicative interaction by using lexical means that demonstrate his erudition. We consider the use of words of foreign origin and vulgarisms as one of the strategies of veiling when a man cares about saving his face and uses vocabulary that is not understandable for a female character.

Features of professional vocabulary in the gender aspect.

The plays chosen for analysis describe the personal and everyday lives of members of modern English society, so the professional activities of the characters play a significant role in them. However, these plays still use everyday vocabulary that belongs to the sphere of the characters' professional interests. For example, when it comes to car breakdowns:

GRAHAM. One of the piston rings has come away from the spurious fugitator (Rayburn, 1977, p. 6).

There are some gender-related differences in the use of professionalism. Using nomenclature vocabulary to refer to objects and subjects belonging to a particular sphere of human activity, most often professional, is more typical for the verbal behavior of male characters in intergender communication. For example, in the communicative interaction of a married couple:

GRAHAM. I'd much rather sit comfortably indoors and listen to your mother, who obviously knows more about the workings of the internal combustion engine than I do (Rayburn, 1977, p. 17).

The male characters' utterances are characterized by the desire for precision in the nomination and vocabulary related to professional activities and technology in everyday life (84% of such vocabulary is used in their verbal behavior). For example, in a conversation between a male character and his mistress:

"GRAHAM. It's a phase I'm going through (Rayburn, 1977: 2);

GRAHAM. I'm not fitted with a thermostat (Rayburn, 1977, p. 2).

Using professional vocabulary in a community of people of the same profession is one of the positive politeness strategies to create an atmosphere of intra-group identity. However, in the studied material, which includes situations of intergender informal communication between spouses, lovers, and acquaintances who are not representatives of the same profession, we consider the use of professional vocabulary as an element of the strategy of veiling. In this case, professional vocabulary reflects the male character's desire to impress and mislead the female character. For example, here is

what the male character tells his mistress about his conversation with his wife:

GRAHAM. I've blinded her with science. She thinks I'm resting with my diatonic resistors (Rayburn, 1977, p. 18).

The statements of a female character can demonstrate her negative attitude to the use of nomenclature by a male character, which takes place, for example, in the situation of communication between lovers:

GRAHAM. Ask me anything about superheterodyne frequency converters.

ELLIE. No, thanks.

GRAHAM. You take no interest in my work (Rayburn, 1977, p. 6).

The use of fictional nomenclature to create a humorous effect and to express their attitude to the vocabulary related to technology characterizes the verbal behavior of female characters. For example, a female character advises her lover to limp if he wants to convince his wife that he has bruised himself:

ELLIE. Bruised coccyx. You've got to make it convincing. You don't want her to think that you're really made of polyphosphoglyceraldepodge (Rayburn, 1977, p. 25).

When explaining unknown concepts, female characters use means that reduce the categorical nature of their statements, which demonstrates their desire not to hurt the male interlocutor's pride. For example, in the communicative interaction between characters who have recently met, the female interlocutor uses you know to reduce the categorical nature of the statement by explaining a term unknown to the male interlocutor:

EVA. I am all id.

REX. What's that?

EVA. You know, the primitive part of your personality (Manktelow, 1979, p. 26).

The use of nomenclature vocabulary in the male characters' remarks reflects the stereotype of the greater importance of the professional factor in the activities of middle-class men. It shows how vital nomenclature vocabulary is in the linguistic worldview of male characters. In addition, vocabulary that female interlocutors do not understand allows male characters to mislead them and achieve specific, pragmatic goals. The misunderstanding and non-use of nomenclature related to technology by female characters reflect the gender stereotype that women have a different sphere of interest.

The use of parables.

Parables combine proverbs and sayings with direct and allegorical meanings and are products of folk art that reflect the wisdom of the people and the values of their worldview. Most often, these are paradoxical maxims that express value judgments and prescriptions of a figurative and non-figurative nature. The phraseological nature of these units reflects their reproducibility, and their duality is idiomatic concerning the direct meaning expressed in the literal meaning of such statements.

A proverb is a short, epigrammatic statement that expresses a well-known wisdom, truth, or moral lesson in an allegorical manner. A proverb is a sentence with a didactic purpose to teach, warn, or caution. A proverb is a communicative phraseological unit that does not

have the character of proverbs. By their very nature, proverbs and sayings constitute a code of moral rules and assessments of life.

The gender analysis of characters' statements in classical dramatic works shows that in informal intergender communication, using parables as one of the strategies of veiling is characteristic of the remarks of male characters and is not typical of the verbal behavior of female characters. Thus, 75% of all paraphrases are used in the statements of male characters. For example, in the communicative interaction of a male character with an acquaintance:

GEORGE. Handsome is as handsome does (Manktelow, 1979, p.13).

During a conversation between a married couple:

RON. Still waters run deep (Daniels, 1986, p. 6);

To remove the instructive nature of the paraphrase in the statements of male characters, it is possible to paraphrase it. For example, a new interpretation of the well-known paraphrase An apple a day keeps the doctor away from the conversation of a married couple:

TREVOR. ...a screw a day keeps the tax man away (Daniels, 1986, p. 27).

The fact that in the situation of informal intergender communication, the use of paraphrases is more typical for the verbal behavior of male characters reflects the communicative stereotype of men's desire for instructional and authoritarianism when communicating with women. Thus, paraphrases are avoided in the remarks of female characters precisely because of their instructive nature.

Conclusion.

A dramatic work combining the features of the language of fiction and colloquial speech is a communication created by a playwright based on real communication. The choice of English dramatic works written in the 1970s-90s as the object of study allows us to analyze the character speech created by playwrights in terms of gender differences. The authors of dramatic works appear as informants who implement their knowledge of the peculiarities of gender manifestation in the statements of characters of opposite sexes. The authors of dramatic works, when creating a character's linguistic characterization, take into account the fact that gender differentiation of people's communicative behavior is based on psychological differences between the sexes, socio-historical peculiarities of the sexes' life, differences in their linguistic worldviews, levels of communicative competence and communicative and pragmatic norms.

Our analysis of characters' statements in modern dramatic works shows that the communicative behavior of characters in informal intergender communication, when the characters play the roles of spouses, lovers, friends, and relatives, has gender pragmatic differences. The analysis of these differences allowed us to identify several aspects:

- gender differences in communication;
- gender differences in the implementation of speech acts;
- gender differences in non-verbal communication behavior.

Consideration of the playwright's use of gender differences in non-verbal communication behavior shows that female characters express their emotions more widely through non-verbal means. When describing the non-verbal behavior of male characters, playwrights demonstrate the emotional restraint of the former and the absence of emotions that convey the character's powerlessness to control the situation (nervousness, fear, pleading, fright).

The playwrights' choice of lexical and stylistic means to create female verbal behavior is due to women's greater stereotypical sensitivity to the moral norms of society, uncritical assessment of the surrounding reality, general uncertainty about the correctness of their perception of the world, the peculiarities of organizing the linguistic picture of the world and the level of linguistic competence.

The authors' choice of lexical and stylistic means to reflect male verbal behavior is determined by the playwrights' ideas about the gender stereotype of men's traditional critical attitude to reality, ignoring the norms of behavior accepted in society, as well as their knowledge of the peculiarities of the organization of the linguistic worldview and the competence of representatives of the opposite sexes. The use of these lexical and stylistic means results in the image of a male character who demonstrates a critical attitude to reality, ignoring the norms of social behavior, a desire to disguise the meaning of a statement, confidence in the correctness of his views, and the instructive nature of communication.

Today, there is every reason to assert that there are feelings that only women or men experience. Therefore, according to these guidelines, there is a choice of language tools that is natural for some and irrelevant, optional for others. This study is not exhaustive. It aims to show the deep connections between language and gender, the subject of gender linguistics.

References

1. Бессонова О.Л. Оцінний тезаурус англійської мови: когнітивно-гендерні аспекти. –

Донецьк: ДонНУ, 2002. 362 с. [Biessonova O.L. Otsinnyi tezaurus anhliiskoi movy: kognityvno-henderni aspekty. – Donetsk: DonNu, 2002. 362 s., in Ukrainian].

2. Борисенко Н.Д. Проблема статевої диференціації сучасного англійського мовлення // Актуальні питання вивчення мови, мовлення і перекладу: Вісник КДЛУ. Дослідження молодих вчених. Сер. Філологія. К.: Київ. держ. лінгв. ун-т. 1997. Вип. 2. С.11-15. [Borysenko N.D. Problema stativoi dyferentsiatsii suchasnoho anhliiskoho movlennia // Aktualni pytannia vuvchennia movy, movlennia i perekladu: Visnyk KDLU. Doslidzhennia molodykh vchenykh. Ser. Filolohiia. K.: Kyiv. derzh. linhv. un-t. 1997. Vyp. 2. S.11-15., in Ukrainian].

3. Вілкова О.Ю. Конструктивні та деструктивні функції гендерних стереотипів: автореф. дис. на здобуття ступеня канд. філол. н. К. 2005. С.18. [Vilkova O.Iu. Konstruktyvni ta destruktyvni funktsii hendernykh stereotypiv: avto-ref. dys. na zdobuttia stupenia kand. filol. n. K. 2005. S.18., in Ukrainian].

4. Семашко Т.Ф. Гендерна лінгвістика в системі сучасної мовознавчої науки. Вісник Маріупольського Державного Гуманітарного Університету. Серія: Філологія, 2010, №3. С.166-170. [Semashko T.F. Henderna linhvistyka v systemi suchasnoi movoznavchoi nauky. Visnyk Mariupolskoho Derzhavnoho Humanitarnoho Universytetu. Seria: Filolohiia, 2010, №3. S.166-170., in Ukrainian].

5. Мартинюк А. П. Конструювання гендеру в англійському дискурсі: [монографія] / А. П. Мартинюк, Харків: Константа. 2004. 292 с. [Martyniuk A. P. Konstruiuvannia henderu v anhlovnomu dyskursi: [monohrafiia] / A. P. Martyniuk, Kharkiv: Konstanta. 2004. 292 s., in Ukrainian].

6. Lakoff, R. Language and Women's Place. New York: Harper and Row. 1975. 328 p.

7. Talbot M. Language and Gender: An Introduction. Cambridge: Polity 2010. 273 p.